

Queue-Less and Cashless Retail Shopping: A Study on Customer Awareness and Acceptance of Emerging Smart Shopping Technologies

Dimple, Jyoti Kushwah, Manisha Tak, Neeharika singh

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT: In today's world due to rapid development of new shopping trends. The retailers launch new technologies for new shopping trends. In today's scenario everyone is busy. When we are talking about shopping from stores, shopping malls etc., the customers wait in the queue for a long time for the payment process. This is a problematic condition for customers. The traditional shopping trend consumes more time during shopping. To remove this problem many retailers are focussing on how to save the time of customers during shopping and payment process. For this purpose many latest and emerging technologies like Near field communications (NFC) technology, image sensing cameras, computer vision, sensor fusion and Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence etc. have brought a new wave of techniques to the retail industry to attract and interact with customers in innovative ways. In today's scenario the demand for smartphones is increasing day by day. Many Smartphones have NFC technology. Therefore with the help of these types of NFC enabled smartphones it can change the way of shopping. Therefore in this paper firstly, the author(s) wants to make the customers aware about the latest shopping updates and technology in customers' shopping delight. Secondly, we know from customers what they feel about queue-less, cashless shopping experience, for this purpose we have designed a set of questionnaires. The questionnaire is filled only by those customers who are

really interested in the same. These technologies will help to improve traditional shopping. Using these technologies no checkout, no queues, no cashier required in shopping malls and stores.

Key Words: NFC, image sensing cameras, computer vision, sensor fusion and Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence, RFID, Smartphones, Shopping malls, Survey

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world due to rapid development of new shopping trends. The retailer launches new technologies for shopping. In today's scenario everyone is busy. When we are talking about shopping from stores, shopping malls etc., the customers wait in the queue for a long time for the payment process. This is a problematic condition for customers. The traditional shopping trend consumes more time during shopping. To remove this problem many retailers are focussing on how to save the time of customers during shopping and payment process. For this purpose many latest and emerging technologies like Near field communications (NFC) technology, image sensing cameras, computer vision, sensor fusion and Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence etc. have brought a new wave of techniques to the retail industry to attract and interact with customers in innovative ways. In today's scenario the demand for smartphones is increasing day by day. Recently many Smartphones have NFC technology. Therefore with the help of these types of NFC enabled smartphones it can change the way of traditional shopping. These technologies will help to improve traditional shopping. Using these technologies no checkout, no queues, no cashier required in shopping malls and stores. Many retailers launch new technologies for new shopping trends For example Amazon Go: It is a new kind of store with no checkout required. With this advanced shopping technology customers never have to wait in line. Just walk out shopping experience, simply use the Amazon Go APP to enter the store. Take the product you want and go. No lines, No checkout, No cash register, simply take and Go. Therefore in this paper firstly, we discuss NFC technology and how this technology will work along with other technology like image sensing cameras, computer vision, sensor fusion and Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence etc. in shopping malls and stores. Secondly, the author(s) wants to make the customers of shopping malls like Big Bazaar and Reliance market, VMart, Vishal Mega Mart, retail store etc. about the latest shopping updates in customers' shopping delight. We will also know from customers what they feel about queueless, cashless shopping experience, for this purpose we have designed a set of questionnaires. The questionnaire is

filled by the customers only from those who are really interested in the same. We will also show the Amazon Go video downloaded from youtube to the interested customers for the reference of No lines, No checkout, No cash register, simply take and Go. Therefore with the help of questionnaires, Amazon Go video etc. we want to introduce to customers about some type of new technology to be implemented in shopping malls.

II. HOW TECHNOLOGY WILL WORK IN SHOPPING MALLS

An NFC enabled smartphone is required to use these types of technology. An app installed in smartphones via presenting a barcode to a sensor. The barcode consists of other sensor technology like GPS etc. It tracks to the customers that he/she entered the store. It identifies the movement of customers and then identifies what product the customer picks up. In stores or shopping malls some new technology will also be used like image recognition combined with a sensor fusion. This technology has confirmed the order and totaled it up. Therefore in the near future all the shopping malls and retail stores will use a number of advanced technologies like image sensing cameras, computer vision, sensor fusion and Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence etc. These technologies could help the customers for checkout free shopping, no queues, No cash register, simply take and Go like Amazon Go.

III. DIFFERENT TYPES OF TECHNOLOGY USED FOR SHOPPING

1. NFC TECHNOLOGY

NFC (near field communication) is a short-range wireless connectivity technology (less than 10 cm) that is used for the exchange of data between two electronic devices. It operates at 13.56 MHz frequency. NFC is designed to be a secure form of data exchange. One of the devices in the NFC network is known as 'NFC tag' and the other device is known as 'NFC reader'. This unique feature allows NFC devices to communicate peer-to-peer. NFC technology is the upgrade of RFID (radio frequency identification) standard technology. It uses the principle of electromagnetic induction between two loop antennas for establishing communication. The connection of NFC is established in a few seconds. The frequency range of NFC falls under unlicensed radio frequency bands. It is considered as an ISM band. NFC can also work when one of the devices is not powered by a battery [1].

1.1 How NFC technology will work in shopping malls:

For an efficient shopping system, with the help of unique NFC Tags that are used to record the article name, number, location of goods placed. Phones with NFC readers recognize the NFC Tag. NFC could provide Shoppers or customers with more benefits beyond faster payments. On the one hand, NFC based Rebate coupons and loyalty cards could further accelerate the check-out process. On the other hand, NFC devices could be used to support customers with more Information on available products. This could also reduce the customers' need for store personnel assistance. Therefore with the help of these types of NFC enabled smartphones it can change the way of shopping.

Fig.1: NFC enabled smartphone

2. Computer vision: computer vision system help to detect which items a shopper pulls off a shelf and carries out of the store. Computer vision is an interdisciplinary field that deals with how computers can be made for gaining high-level understanding from digital images or videos. From the perspective of engineering, it seeks to automate tasks that the human visual system can do. [2]. It allows the computer not only to record images but also to interpret them.
3. Image recognition and Sensor fusion: in shopping malls we can identify the products using image recognition. Combine this with the Fusion Sensors that cross confirm the new virtual "shopping cart" we can create not only just by taking an item in our hand, but also by putting it back, there is actually even less of a likelihood of an erroneous transaction. It is a process by which data from several different sensors are "fused" to compute

something more than could be determined by any one sensor alone. An example is computing the orientation of a device in three-dimensional space. That data might then be used to alter the perspective presented by a 3D GUI or game.

4. Machine learning algorithm, Artificial Intelligence:

Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and deep learning garnered from decades of being a retailer. It starts with the hardware that includes image sensors using camera optics, LIDAR arrays using laser sensing and other technology to correctly identify the item on a shelf, taken off the shelf, returned back to the shelf or taken out of the store. [3]

Fig. 2: figure shows the Impact of AI on the retail industry
Source: <https://yourstory.com/2017/01/impact-ai-retail-industry/>

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning both are at the forefront of technical innovation. Machine learning is a subset of artificial intelligence that uses algorithms to learn from data sets. Algorithms are essentially a series of steps that lead to the completion of a task. Using data and algorithms, Machine learning technologies make intelligent predictions or perform actions. In machine learning, the framework is developed and data is provided, so that machines can teach themselves what they need to know and understand what to do [4].

5. RFID (Radio frequency identification): It is a new technology which uses an electromagnetic field to track and identify tags attached to the object. The tags are small in size that emit distinct signals. Small Tags contain electronically stored information.

Fig.3: figure shows RFID technology

Shopping malls and Retail stores can use this technology to record or store a variety of information such as quantities of various items that are available in store, serial number, their locations, purchase record etc.. The tags can be attached to all sorts of things. With the help of this technology the customer will have the information about the price of every item that is scanned in, total price of the item, detail of product etc. This technology will save customers time of customers, cost, manpower etc. that is required in shopping malls and retail stores.

Smart Trolley using RFID can also be used for shopping. In shopping malls the technology will work by simply attaching RFID tags to the products and a RFID reader with a LCD display on the shopping trolley. It has two types: passive and active. Tags are used to identify the object and tied with them. Active tags send radio waves to the RFID reader and hence will inform about its location. Passive tags reflect the radio waves transmitted by RFID reader and hence reader will come to know about location of the tags.

Fig.4: figure shows Smart Trolley using RFID
Source: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/smart-retail-stores-ensuring-bestcustomer-experience-rowan-klaiber>

V. MANY RETAILERS WORK ON NFC TECHNOLOGY

Amazon Go is the latest example which is also considering creating NFC-based marketing services.

Amazon already offers an application for Apple's iPhone, called Price Check by Amazon, that lets consumers compare prices of in-store items with Amazon's by scanning bar codes, snapping pictures, or saying or typing the product's name.

Google brought it to market first with the Nexus S and now have jumped on board with the Near Field Communications Forum.

Microsoft is already planning to enable NFC technology in soon-to-be-released Windows Phone 7 models; even Apple has been focusing on their game by paving the way for iPhone and other iOS devices to embed NFC-reader chips.

In fact, outfits like Google and Amazon would find huge benefit if they decided to partner with retail establishments by tailoring not just NFC but hyper local marketing to permit retail stores to transmit and/or allow access to their daily deals via smartphones [5].

VI. SURVEY DONE IN SHOPPING MALLS FOR REALISTIC VIEW OF CUSTOMERS

We have done a survey in various shopping malls/retail store like Big Bazaar and Reliance market, VMart, Vishal Mega Mart, retail store etc. of Ajmer. We awarding the customers about future technology to be implemented in near future in developed countries to know about the technology and seeking the answers of the questions that the shopping malls and customers are ready to adept forthcoming technological changes and revolution in shopping trend.

Image 1: Survey done in shopping mall.

Image 2: Survey done in shopping mall.

Image 3: Survey done in shopping mall.

Image 4: Acquire shopping experiences of customers.

Image 5 : Survey outside the Reliance Fresh

Image 6: Providing awareness to the customers in shopping malls about the new shopping trends

Image 7: letter for survey visit

Image 8: letter for survey visit

Image 12: letter for survey visit

VII. SURVEY RESULT

Image 9: letter for survey visit

Image 10: letter for survey visit

Image 11: letter for survey visit

Results for: An empirical study of Using new technology like NFC, AI, RFID in Shopping malls in Ajmer to ease out the customer shopping experience like queue less n cashless payment mode

VIII. DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

In this paper the online survey was conducted for seeking the awareness of new technology like NFC, AI, RFID in Shopping malls in Ajmer to ease out the customer shopping experience like queue less and cashless payment mode.

The age and income group questions were excluded from the questionnaire as any person of any age group and any income group who possesses a smartphone can purchase goods from the Hi-Tech store without making payment in cash and the customer could be any person irrespective of his/her age group. The author (s) has taken two steps ahead by excluding the regular features of questionnaires like age group, male or female and income group.

In this survey in response to the question regarding do you have a smartphone? Out of 289 respondents 82.35% own smartphones as people are aware of usage of smartphones with the latest 4th generation of communication available for mobile technology. In response to the question regarding NFC enabled smartphones 43.66 percent have NFC enabled smartphones or they know about NFC but about 56% respondents do not know about this feature of their smartphone and 5 respondent skipped this question due to lack of knowledge. In response to the question regarding visit to shopping malls, 4 respondents skipped this question and 285 respondents gave responses to this question. According to them, about 20% of them visit more than 4 times to shop in a shopping mall, 28% visit between 2-4 times and 29% visit 2-3 times. 22 percent make this visit in a month to shop from the above mentioned data, the frequency of visitors is more if we combine 2-3 and 2-4 times visitors that makes 29% + 28%=57 percent. This is a huge amount of the population who makes the purchase and stands in the queue for shopping and billing.

In India the shopping trends are shifting from regular market to shopping mall culture; due to new generation and double income group family standards, they prefer to shop in shopping malls and variety of brand availability. They are the target customers for the new Hi-Tech shopping mall in future.

The experience in shopping mall is very time consuming in comparison to traditional shopping as the variety of goods and offers made by companies and shopping malls too makes the choice difficult and the queue at cash register is always a time consuming feature of any shopping mall, 79 percent respondent support this through of time consuming affair in shopping through shopping mall.

Shopping experience in shopping malls is rated by 289 respondents in which 19% says it much better, 39 percent says it is a better experience and 29% are neutral and about 10 percent are in support of work experience. The above facts of information implicates that around 30 percent are not supportive. They purchase from shopping malls due to various reasons but they are not happy with their shopping experience. It may be due to the billing procedure or other things who are in support of this.

In response to the question regarding selection of products with various discount schemes, only 13 percent support the reason about the selection of goods with different discount schemes available there. The information derived from the above facts is that people are very much disturbed due to the long billing queue but they do not have any alternatives except to stand in a row and wait for their turn.

This billing queue phenomenon is growing day by day from metro to tier-2 and tier-3 cities but people do not find any suitable solution for it. This gives the researcher the 'research gap' to be fully filled by using the technology. As it is very clear from earlier questions that people are having smartphones and most of them are aware of using technology on smartphones.

In regard to queue less and cashless shopping the respondents are very much in support about 86 percent are in support of this and 14 percent say 'no', maybe these respondents are those who come only 'once' and when they are only 'once' type of customers. The billing queue doesn't affect them more in comparison to those who came frequently to shop in shopping malls.

While standing in the billing queue makes the person boring according to 40 percent of respondents. Tiring 33 percent as the customers can be of any age group from children to old age. Those standing in the queue are definitely tiring. Having more cash registers that are supported by 9 percent respondents is a temporary solution to divide the surge in festival season but having extra manpower during normal season is a cost increasing issue to shopping malls. 16 percent of respondents support having a new technology to shorten the billing queue.

In response to the question, if there is no billing queue and cash register would they prefer to shop from that shopping mall/store out of 289 respondents 40 percent strongly agree, 36 percent agree and 14 percent they have enough time to stand in a queue and 7 percent disagree and 1 percent strongly disagree. It is very clear from the situation above 40+36=76 percent are in support of cashless/queue less shopping experience and for those who do not agree the percent is low and may be they are 'once' times and may be they

do not have smartphones or probably do not know how to use new technology for their betterment.

79 percent of respondents are in support of the question regarding some new change/trends in shopping experiences; only 5 percent are not in support of change and 14 percent neutral due to any reason they do not want to change or do not wish to be a part in new changes in shopping mall experience.

In response to the question about using new technology like NFC, AI, etc. for purchasing and payment procedures out of 289 respondents 87 percent are in support of the question about 12 percent say 'No'. The huge percent of support indicates that people want change and they wish to use new technology for their shopping experience as new generations are already using web portals for online shopping and facilities like cash on delivery options to make their shopping experience easier.

In response to the question regarding technologies that should be implemented in shopping malls, nearly 87 percent of respondents are in support of the question. Only 12 percent of respondents said 'no'. It is clear that the huge percentage of support indicates that people want change and they wish to use new technology for their shopping.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper we concluded that with the help of new technology like NFC, AI, RFID in Shopping malls, it will change the way of shopping in future. Because in the current scenario every person is busy and they want to spend minimum time for shopping processes like billing, standing in queue etc.. So in this paper with the help of a survey we find that most people want to upgrade the traditional way of shopping. In this research paper we had surveyed many malls of Ajmer like Reliance market, V-Mart, Vishal Mega Mart, Big Bazaar and retail stores also. Some of the malls did not give us the permission for surveys in their malls like Big Bazaar, Vishal Mega Mart. So we had done the survey outside the shopping malls. During the survey we found that the customers are not aware of these kinds of technologies. Most of the customers had NFC enabled mobile phones but they are not aware that their phones are NFC enabled or not. With the help of surveys we aware them about these technologies and how these technologies will be beneficial for shopping in future.

The managers of the malls also show their positive and helpful response for giving us permission to do a survey and they also appreciate these kinds of

technologies. They want to implement these kinds of technologies in the future for provide better services to their customers.

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